
Progress report from Working Group 2 - *Understanding the Open Science Monitoring Landscape* - March 2026

1. General information

Names of co-chairs: Lamis Elkheir & Tereza Szybisty

Initial objectives: WG2's work is guided by the OSMI Principles of Open Science Monitoring and contributes to a clearer understanding of what is currently being monitored, by whom, and how.

- To identify existing Open Science monitoring initiatives worldwide
- To consolidate existing lists and avoid duplication of efforts
- To build a structured dataset enabling descriptive and comparative analysis

2. Summary of the group's activities since its creation

Number and dates of meetings:

- Number of meetings held: 8
- Meeting frequency: Monthly
- Average participation: Approximately 15-20 members per meeting

Key points of discussion, methodologies and outputs.

- Agreed on a shared definition of an Open Science monitoring initiative, aligned with the OSMI Principles and endorsed by OSMI leadership.
- Collected initiatives through WG member contributions and by reviewing existing initiative lists maintained by organisations and infrastructures.
- Consolidated and deduplicated these sources into a single harmonised dataset with defined classification fields.
- Extracted structured information for each initiative, including geographic scope, organisational leadership, Open Science areas monitored, data sources, and monitoring approaches, followed by internal review and validation.
- Identified 72 Open Science monitoring initiatives worldwide, creating a dataset that enables descriptive and comparative analysis of current monitoring practices.

Prepared the dataset for [public community review](#) through a [read-only dataset](#) and [feedback form](#), allowing corrections, additions, and identification of missing initiatives.

3. Challenges, upcoming activities, deliverables, timeline and working group duration

Challenges:

- Active contribution was concentrated among a smaller subset of WG members than initially anticipated, which affected the pace of data extraction and review
- Identifying initiatives required significant manual searching and cross-referencing across fragmented sources
- Consolidating and harmonising multiple pre-existing lists (with overlapping and inconsistent entries) required substantial effort to remove duplication and ensure alignment
- Early community use of the preliminary dataset - need to clarify licensing.

Planned Deliverables

- **Landscape Analysis Report:** A structured report presenting the findings of the descriptive analysis, including patterns, coverage, gaps, and governance linkages across Open Science monitoring initiatives.
- **Visual Output:** A set of clear visual summaries (e.g., charts, comparative tables, or a dashboard-style overview) to support communication and interpretation of the findings.
- **Potential Academic or Policy Publication:** A possible peer-reviewed or policy-oriented paper based on the dataset and analysis, depending on the outcomes of the analytical phase and strategic alignment within OSMI.

Upcoming Activities and Timeline

Period	Activity
March 2026	Public review phase (two-week consultation window) to collect corrections, additions, and missing initiatives from the Open Science community.
April 2026	Incorporation of community feedback and final validation of the consolidated dataset.
May – June 2026	Descriptive landscape analysis of identified initiatives, including patterns, geographic distribution, organisational trends, coverage across Open Science pillars, and potential gaps.
May 2026 (launch)	Webinar series: <i>Open Science Monitoring Initiative Deep Dives</i> (potentially open to the public). The series will invite representatives from different Open Science monitoring initiatives to present their approaches

Autumn 2026	Preparation of a potential academic or policy-oriented publication presenting the results of the WG2 analysis.
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